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Individuals with Overall Digital Skills Above Basic Levels in Italian Regions

Individuals with overall digital skills above basic levels in the Italian regions have grown on average by 1.49% between 2018 and 2023. The European Innovation Scoreboard calculates individuals with overall digital skills above basic levels, defined as the number of individuals with such skills (Eurostat: EU survey on ICT use in households and by individuals). Overall digital skills represent the highest level of the composite digital skills indicator, based on selected activities performed by individuals aged 16 to 74 on the Internet in four specific areas (information, communication, problem-solving, content creation) during the preceding three months. The data refers to the 20 Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Individuals with Overall Digital Skills Above Basic Levels in 2023. The analysis of data on individuals with overall digital skills above basic levels in 2023 provides a detailed picture of the spread of digital skills across Italian regions. There is a significant variation between different geographical areas, with Emilia Romagna leading the ranking with 87.04% of the population possessing advanced digital skills, indicative of a socio-economic environment highly conducive to innovation and the adoption of new technologies. Other regions in the North and Center, such as Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Lombardy, and Trentino Alto Adige, show high percentages, all above 84%, reflecting strong digital infrastructure and effective regional policies promoting digital literacy. These areas likely benefit from greater access to educational resources, continuous training initiatives, and job opportunities that require or develop such skills. In contrast, Puglia, Calabria, and Sicily record the lowest values, with percentages around 74%. This highlights the challenges that Southern Italian regions face in promoting digital education and fully integrating digital skills into the workforce. The discrepancy between North and South emphasizes differences in infrastructure and technology investments and the need for targeted policies to overcome the digital divide. It is interesting to note that regions with smaller sizes and populations, such as Valle d'Aosta and Sardinia, show remarkable commitment to digital literacy, with percentages exceeding 80%. This could be attributed to specific regional programs aimed at maximizing the impact of digital training initiatives on the population.

Individuals with Overall Digital Skills Above Basic Levels between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of data on individuals with overall digital skills above basic levels between 2018 and 2023 in Italian regions reveals a mixed picture, with significant variations both in absolute and percentage terms. Some regions, such as Basilicata, Calabria, and Campania, have experienced a marked increase in digital skills, with percentage changes ranging from 7.61% to 11.12%. This suggests a significant

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improvement in the digital skills of the population in these areas, perhaps due to targeted digital education policies or increased access to technology. Conversely, regions such as Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, and Lombardy have seen a reduction in digital skills, with negative percentage changes indicating a slight regression in this area. This could result from various factors, including changes in demographic composition, availability of continuous training, or the focus of regional policies. It is interesting to note that regions such as Lazio and Trentino Alto Adige have recorded positive, albeit modest, variations, indicating stability or slight improvement in digital skills. This could reflect an already high digitalization context or the effectiveness of training and professional updating programs. The observed variations among different regions suggest that the regional context, training policies, access to technology, and digitalization efforts significantly impact the population's digital skills.

Italian Macro-regions. The analysis of data on digital skills in Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2023 shows a differentiated evolution reflecting the socio-economic dynamics and training policies adopted in different areas of the country. In the South, there is a tangible improvement, with an increase of 3.17% in absolute terms and 4.65% in percentage terms of digital skills above basic levels. This increase may indicate the effectiveness of digitalization programs and educational initiatives aimed at improving digital literacy. It could also reflect a growing recognition of the importance of digital skills for social inclusion and employability, especially in a region traditionally considered less advanced in technological terms. Conversely, in the North and Center, variations are marginal and practically nil, with a slight decrease of 0.02% for the North and 0.00% for the Center. These data suggest that these macro-regions, already more advanced in digital skills in 2018, have maintained their levels without significant improvements. The near-stagnation in these areas may reflect a saturation of digital skills among the population or indicate the need to renew or intensify training efforts to keep pace with increasingly advanced and rapidly evolving technologies. This scenario highlights the importance of not considering digital skills progress as a given, even in the most advanced regions. It is essential to continue investing in training and professional updating to keep pace with the digital transformations characterizing the contemporary economy and society. At the same time, the increase in digital skills in the South offers a positive note, suggesting that targeted policies and investments in this sector can produce substantial improvements, contributing to reducing the digital divide between different areas of the country.

North-South Divide. Data on overall digital skills above basic levels between 2018 and 2023 in Italian macro-regions reveal a North-South divide, albeit in a dynamic form showing signs of change. Initially, the North had a higher level of digital skills (84.17%) compared to the South (73.66%), confirming the presence of a digital divide reflecting historical socio-economic disparities between the two areas. However, over these five years, the South has recorded a significant increase in digital skills, with an increase of 3.17 percentage points (4.65% percentage increase), while the North has seen a very slight decrease (-0.18 percentage points, -0.02%). This improvement in the South may indicate that initiatives and investments in improving access to technology and digital training are beginning to bear fruit, helping to reduce the digital divide. On the other hand, the stagnation observed in the North and Center may reflect a situation of saturation or indicate the need to renew training efforts to keep pace with technological developments. Although the data show that the divide is narrowing, the presence of a difference in digital skills between North and South persists, highlighting the need to continue directing resources and specific strategies to overcome disparities. Furthermore,

this digital divide is only one of the multiple dimensions of regional disparities in Italy, which also include differences in income, unemployment rates, access to education and healthcare, and the quality of infrastructure. Reducing the North-South divide, therefore, requires a holistic approach that addresses all these issues in a coordinated manner, aiming for more balanced and inclusive growth across the national territory.

Economic Policies to Increase the Presence of Individuals with Above Average Digital Skills. To enhance the level of above-average digital skills in Italian regions, it is crucial for economic policies to focus on a holistic and integrated approach that spans from basic education to continuous professional training, including significant investments in infrastructure and digital inclusion programs. Expanding access to high-speed internet across the national territory is fundamental, eliminating existing disparities and ensuring that every individual has the same opportunities for digital learning. Integrating curricula dedicated to digital literacy in schools from the early stages prepares future generations to face the challenges of an increasingly technological world, developing advanced skills in fields such as programming, cybersecurity, and data analysis. It is also essential to promote professional training and retraining programs for adults and workers, encouraging companies to invest in the digital training of their employees and create apprenticeship opportunities in the technology sector. The creation of centers of excellence and technological hubs in universities stimulates innovation and facilitates the transfer of knowledge from academia to the productive fabric, thereby strengthening the country's innovative ecosystem. Initiatives aimed at digital inclusion should focus on bridging the digital divide, especially for people in disadvantaged or rural areas, providing access to technological devices and digital literacy courses. Promoting public-private partnerships can amplify the effectiveness of these policies, sharing resources and best practices among various economic and social actors. Finally, awareness campaigns on the value of digital skills can motivate individuals of all ages to engage in learning and training pathways, emphasizing how these skills are fundamental for personal and professional growth and for the progress of society as a whole. By adopting these strategies, Italy could significantly elevate the level of digital skills of its population, promoting economic growth, increasing the competitiveness of its companies, and ensuring greater social cohesion, ready to face the challenges of the digital era with confidence.

Conclusions. The value of individuals with above-average digital skills grew by 1.49% between 2018 and 2023. Looking at the Italian macro-regions, this value grew only in Southern Italy, with a growth of +4.65% between 2018 and 2023. Conversely, the North experienced a slight negative decrease of -0.02%, while in Central Italy, this value remained unchanged. However, from a strictly numerical point of view, there remains a significant difference between the Central-Northern regions, which have values of the observed variable equal to 83.98, and the South, which has values equal to 76.83. The increase in basic digital skills is absolutely necessary to enable the population to effectively use new technologies both in the exercise of citizenship rights and for income and employment prospects.

Declarations

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Appendix

